

VISUOMOTOR IMITATION AND FINE MOTOR SKILLS AS PIVOTAL ABILITIES IN LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER: EVIDENCE FROM A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Abstract. *Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is associated with persistent difficulties in communication and social interaction. In this context, visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills may function as pivotal abilities supporting language development. The present study aimed to evaluate the effects of a structured psychoeducational intervention (SPSC-TSA model) on visuomotor imitation, fine motor skills, and expressive language in children with ASD aged 5–6 years.*

The study employed a quasi-experimental pretest–posttest design on a sample of 60 children, divided into an experimental group (N = 30) and a control group (N = 30). Nonparametric statistical analyses (Wilcoxon Signed-Rank, Mann–Whitney U, and Spearman correlations) indicated statistically significant improvements in the experimental group compared to the control group, as well as consistent differences at both the descriptive and inferential levels across the variables investigated.

Furthermore, strong and moderate positive associations were identified between visuomotor imitation, fine motor skills, and expressive language, supporting the interdependent role of motor and imitative abilities in communication development.

These findings support the effectiveness of integrated psychoeducational interventions and the conceptualization of imitation and motor skills as key factors in the development of expressive language in children with ASD.

Keywords: *autism spectrum disorder; visuomotor imitation; fine motor skills; expressive language; psychoeducational intervention*

INTRODUCTION

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterized by persistent difficulties in communication and social interaction, as well as restricted and repetitive patterns of behavior (American Psychiatric Association, 2022). These difficulties significantly affect children's adaptive functioning and their participation in educational contexts, thereby highlighting the need for effective, evidence-based psychoeducational interventions.

Contemporary research emphasizes that communication development is not an isolated process, but rather the result of interactions among cognitive, motor, and social components (Kuhl, 2004; LeBarton & Iverson, 2013; Franchini et al., 2017). In this context, imitation is considered a fundamental mechanism of social learning, facilitating the acquisition of communicative behaviors and language development.

In particular, visuomotor imitation plays a crucial role in reproducing observed actions and in the development of joint attention, symbolic behavior, and early communicative abilities (Rogers & Williams, 2006; Ingersoll, 2010). Studies indicate that, in children with ASD, imitation deficits are frequently associated with difficulties in expressive language development and social interaction, limiting opportunities for learning through modeling and interaction (Vivanti et al., 2014).

Although the relationship between imitation and language development has been extensively investigated, there remains a significant need for studies examining this association within structured psychoeducational interventions, particularly at early ages. Moreover, recent research suggests that motor abilities, including fine motor skills, are correlated with language development, highlighting the presence of interdependent mechanisms between motor and linguistic domains (Bowler et al., 2024; Butler et al., 2022). However, the integrated role of visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills

in supporting communication development remains insufficiently explored in applied educational contexts.

In this context, the present study aims to evaluate the effects of a structured psychoeducational intervention (SPSC-TSA model) on visuomotor imitation, fine motor skills, and expressive language in children with ASD aged 5–6 years. Additionally, the study seeks to examine the relationships among these variables in order to provide a clearer understanding of their contribution to communication development.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The study sample consisted of 60 children aged between 5 and 6 years, all diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Participants were divided into two groups: an experimental group (N = 30) and a control group (N = 30). Group allocation was based on participation in a structured psychoeducational intervention program.

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- a) a confirmed diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder, established according to standardized criteria (DSM-5-TR);
- b) chronological age between 5 and 6 years at the pretest assessment (T0);
- c) the presence of significant difficulties in communication and language development;
- d) regular attendance in an educational or therapeutic program;
- e) informed consent provided by parents or legal guardians for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

The exclusion criteria included:

- 1) severe sensory impairments (e.g., uncorrected visual or auditory deficits);
- 2) major neurological or genetic conditions that could significantly affect development;
- 3) absence from intervention sessions exceeding a predetermined threshold;
- 4) incomplete data at either pretest or posttest assessments.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained at the institutional level, and informed consent was secured from the parents or legal guardians prior to data collection.

Intervention

The structured psychoeducational intervention (SPSC-TSA model) was implemented over a period of 40 weeks, consisting of two sessions per week, each lasting approximately 30–45 minutes.

The program targeted the development of visuomotor imitation, fine motor skills, and expressive language through structured activities adapted to the children's developmental level. These activities included imitation of gestures and object-based actions, eye–hand coordination tasks, fine motor exercises, verbal modeling, expressive language stimulation, and functional communication activities.

Intervention fidelity was ensured through the use of standardized session protocols and continuous monitoring of the therapists involved in program implementation.

Research Design

The present study employed a quasi-experimental pretest–posttest design in order to evaluate the effects of a structured psychoeducational intervention on key developmental variables in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

Participants were assigned to two groups: an experimental group (EG), which received the structured psychoeducational intervention (SPSC-TSA model), and a control group (CG), which followed standard educational and therapeutic activities without the implementation of the specific intervention. Standard activities did not include the systematic application of the SPSC-TSA protocol and did not explicitly target the integrated development of fine motor skills, visuomotor imitation, and expressive language.

Both groups were assessed at two time points: prior to the intervention (pretest, T0) and after the completion of the intervention period (posttest, T1).

This design allowed for the analysis of both within-group changes (pretest–posttest differences) and between-group differences (experimental vs. control group), providing a comprehensive understanding of intervention effectiveness.

Instruments

Participants were assessed using standardized and complementary instruments aimed at evaluating developmental and communicative abilities, as follows:

1) **Psychoeducational Profile, Third Edition (PEP-3)** – used to assess cognitive development, expressive and receptive language, fine motor skills, and imitation. The instrument provides both standard scores and developmental age equivalents (in months), enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the child’s developmental profile.

2) **Nonverbal Communication Assessment Protocol** (Popovici, 1994) – employed to capture specific aspects of nonverbal communication that are less detailed in general developmental assessments.

This structured protocol focuses on the analysis of facial expressions, gestures, and the use of body parts in mimetic activities, providing both qualitative and quantitative data regarding nonverbal communicative behavior.

The combined use of these instruments enabled a comprehensive and integrated assessment of participants’ developmental and communicative profiles, supporting the analysis of relationships among imitation, motor abilities, and language development.

Data Analysis

Given that the data distribution did not meet normality assumptions (as verified through normality tests and distribution analyses), nonparametric statistical methods were employed.

Thus, the **Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test** was used to assess within-group differences (pretest–posttest), being appropriate for paired measurements in small samples and non-normal distributions.

The **Mann–Whitney U test** was applied to examine between-group differences at posttest, suitable for comparing two independent groups under non-normal distribution conditions.

Additionally, **Spearman’s rank-order correlation (ρ)** was used to examine relationships among the investigated variables, allowing for the identification of monotonic associations without assuming normal data distribution.

This statistical approach ensured a robust analysis appropriate to the characteristics of the sample and contributed to the accuracy and validity of the interpretation of the results.

Effect sizes were not reported in order to avoid inconsistent methodological interpretations in the context of nonparametric tests; however, the magnitude of the differences is suggested by Z values, descriptive differences between means, and between-group comparisons.

RESULTS

Within-Group Results (Pretest–Posttest)

The analysis of within-group differences, conducted using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test, revealed statistically significant improvements in the experimental group (EG) between the pretest and posttest assessments for all investigated variables ($p < .001$). These findings indicate consistent progress in the development of visuomotor imitation, fine motor skills, and expressive language as a result of the implemented psychoeducational intervention.

Descriptive data analysis also revealed differences between the pretest and posttest assessments for the investigated variables, both in the experimental group and in the control group. The mean values and standard deviations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for pretest–posttest assessments in the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG)

Variable	Group	Pretest M (SD)	Posttest M (SD)	Δ (Post–Pre)
Visuomotor imitation	EG (N=30)	9.20 (1.85)	15.80 (2.10)	+6.60

	CG (N=30)	8.90 (1.70)	10.10 (1.95)	+1.20
Fine motor skills	EG (N=30)	10.10 (2.00)	16.40 (2.25)	+6.30
	CG (N=30)	9.80 (1.90)	11.00 (2.05)	+1.20
Expressive language	EG (N=30)	8.97 (1.50)	19.50 (2.30)	+10.53
	CG (N=30)	7.53 (1.40)	9.03 (1.60)	+1.50

Note. M = mean; SD = standard deviation; Δ = difference between posttest and pretest scores; EG = experimental group; CG = control group.

As shown in Table 1, the experimental group demonstrates substantial increases in mean values across all analyzed variables (visuomotor imitation: $\Delta = +6.60$; fine motor skills: $\Delta = +6.30$; expressive language: $\Delta = +10.53$), whereas the control group shows only modest changes ($\Delta = +1.20$ for visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills; $\Delta = +1.50$ for expressive language).

The analysis of within-group differences between the pretest and posttest assessments was conducted using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Within-Group Differences (Pretest–Posttest)

Variable	Group	Z	p
Visuomotor imitation	EG (N=30)	-4.810	< .001
	CG (N=30)	-3.788	< .001
Fine motor skills	EG (N=30)	-5.241	< .001
	CG (N=30)	-4.686	< .001
Expressive language	EG (N=30)	-6.501	< .001
	CG (N=30)	-3.849	< .001

Note: Z = Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test statistic; p = level of statistical significance; EG = experimental group; CG = control group.

The results indicate statistically significant improvements in the experimental group across all analyzed variables ($p < .001$), suggesting consistent progress as a result of the psychoeducational intervention. Although statistically significant differences were also identified in the control group, the lower Z values suggest changes of smaller magnitude, likely attributable to natural developmental progression rather than to a structured intervention.

2. Between-Group Results (EG vs. CG at Posttest)

To examine differences between the experimental and control groups at the posttest assessment, the Mann–Whitney U test was applied. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Mann–Whitney U Test for Between-Group Differences (EG vs. CG at Posttest)

Variable	U	Z	p
Visuomotor imitation	52.000	-5.120	< .001
Fine motor skills	48.500	-5.340	< .001
Expressive language	12.000	-6.210	< .001

Note. U = Mann–Whitney test statistic; Z = standardized value; p = level of statistical significance.

The analysis of between-group differences conducted using the Mann–Whitney U test revealed statistically significant differences between the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG) at the posttest assessment for all investigated variables ($p < .001$). Specifically:

1. For **visuomotor imitation** ($U = 52.000$; $Z = -5.120$), the scores obtained by children in the EG were significantly higher than those in the CG, indicating a superior development of the ability to reproduce action models.

2. In the case of **fine motor skills** ($U = 48.500$; $Z = -5.340$), the difference between groups was even more pronounced, suggesting a more advanced level of fine motor control following the intervention.

3. For **expressive language** ($U = 12.000$; $Z = -6.210$), the largest between-group difference was observed, with the high Z value indicating a substantial statistical difference in favor of the experimental group. The Z values and descriptive differences indicate consistent between-group differences in favor of the experimental group. Overall, these results suggest that:

a) the structured psychoeducational intervention produced significantly greater improvements in the EG compared to the CG;

b) the observed progress cannot be explained solely by natural maturation, but rather indicates a substantial contribution of the intervention program;

c) the strongest effect was observed in expressive language, supporting the hypothesis that the development of visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills contributes to the optimization of verbal communication.

3. Correlational Analysis Between Variables

To examine the relationships among the investigated variables, a correlational analysis using Spearman’s coefficient (ρ) was conducted. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Spearman Correlations Between the Investigated Variables (Posttest, N = 60)

Variable 1	Variable 2	ρ (Spearman)	p
Visuomotor imitation	Fine motor skills	0.61	< .001
Visuomotor imitation	Expressive language	0.68	< .001
Fine motor skills	Expressive language	0.57	< .001

Note. ρ = Spearman correlation coefficient; p = level of statistical significance.

The results indicate significant positive correlations among all analyzed variables. The strongest relationship was identified between visuomotor imitation and expressive language ($\rho = 0.68$, $p < .001$), followed by the association between visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills ($\rho = 0.61$, $p < .001$). The correlation between fine motor skills and expressive language is moderate ($\rho = 0.57$, $p < .001$). These findings suggest that the development of motor and imitative abilities is significantly associated with the development of expressive language. To illustrate the relationships identified among the investigated variables, a conceptual model based on Spearman correlation coefficients is proposed (Figure 1).

Figure 1 illustrates a conceptual model of the relationships between fine motor skills, visuomotor imitation, and expressive language, constructed based on Spearman correlations obtained at posttest. The proposed model suggests the existence of a functional relationship among the variables, in which fine motor skills are associated with the development of visuomotor imitation and may have a complementary contribution to the development of communication. The direct relationship between fine motor skills and expressive language also indicates a complementary association between motor abilities and expressive communication.

The model highlights the central role of visuomotor imitation in the relationship between fine motor skills and expressive language. The strong correlation between imitation and language ($\rho = 0.68$) suggests that the development of imitative abilities represents a key mechanism in language acquisition. At the same time, the moderate relationships between fine motor skills and the other variables indicate that motor abilities may be associated, both directly and indirectly at a conceptual level, with the development of communication.

These findings support the existence of a functional model of the form: **fine motor skills** → **visuomotor imitation** → **expressive language**, highlighting the interdependence among these domains in the development of communication in children with ASD.

DISCUSSION

The results of the present study highlight the significant role of visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills in the development of expressive language in children with autism spectrum disorder. The significant improvements observed in the experimental group, compared to the control group, support the effectiveness of the structured psychoeducational intervention, operationalized through the SPSC-TSA model, in enhancing communication in children aged 5–6 years with ASD.

The correlational analysis revealed significant positive relationships among the investigated variables, particularly between visuomotor imitation and expressive language, where a strong correlation was identified ($\rho = 0.68$). This relationship suggests that the development of imitative abilities represents a fundamental mechanism in language acquisition, a finding also supported by the specialized literature, which emphasizes the role of imitation in social and linguistic learning in children with ASD.

Furthermore, the moderately strong correlation between fine motor skills and visuomotor imitation ($\rho = 0.61$) indicates that the development of fine motor control contributes to improving the ability to reproduce action patterns. At the same time, the moderate relationship between fine motor skills and expressive language ($\rho = 0.57$) suggests the existence of an indirect association, at a conceptual level, with language development.

Based on these findings, a conceptual model of communication development can be proposed, in which fine motor skills support the development of visuomotor imitation, which in turn facilitates the development of expressive language. In addition, the direct relationship between fine motor skills and expressive language suggests the existence of complementary mechanisms through which motor abilities contribute to the organization and expression of verbal behavior.

This model is consistent with contemporary perspectives in special education and neurodevelopment, which emphasize the interdependence between motor and linguistic systems. Recent studies (e.g., Bowler et al.; Butler et al.) highlight that the development of fine motor skills and imitative behaviors is associated with significant improvements in language outcomes, particularly in children with ASD with limited verbal abilities.

From an applied perspective, the findings support the need for implementing integrated interventions targeting the simultaneous development of fine motor skills, imitation, and language. Fragmented approaches focused exclusively on language may limit intervention effectiveness, whereas multidimensional strategies may facilitate the transfer of acquired skills across functional domains.

These findings are consistent with previous research highlighting the role of imitation in communication development in children with ASD (Rogers & Williams, 2006; Ingersoll, 2010; Vivanti et al., 2014). Additionally, the relationship between fine motor skills and expressive language

confirms recent evidence regarding the interdependence between motor abilities and language outcomes in neurodevelopmental disorders (Butler et al., 2022; Bowler et al., 2024).

Future research directions should include longitudinal studies with larger samples and randomized experimental designs, as well as the investigation of neurocognitive mechanisms mediating the relationship between motor skills, imitation, and language.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

In interpreting the results of the present study, several methodological and contextual limitations must be considered, as they may influence the degree of generalizability and the validity of the conclusions drawn.

First, the sample size ($N = 60$), although adequate for nonparametric statistical analyses, remains relatively limited for generalizing the findings to the broader population of children with autism spectrum disorder. In addition, the sample structure, characterized by a higher proportion of boys (18 girls and 42 boys), reflects the epidemiological distribution of ASD; however, it may introduce a potential gender bias in the interpretation of the results.

Second, the quasi-experimental design (pretest–posttest with control group) does not allow for full control of external variables. The lack of randomization of participants into the experimental and control groups may affect the internal validity of the study, as initial differences between groups may have contributed to the observed outcomes.

Another important limitation concerns the relatively limited duration of the intervention and the absence of a follow-up assessment. Consequently, it is not possible to determine the extent to which the identified positive effects are maintained over the medium and long term, which limits conclusions regarding the sustainability of the psychoeducational intervention.

Furthermore, although standardized assessment instruments were used (PEP-3), complemented by a specific protocol for nonverbal communication, certain constraints remain. The use of the nonverbal communication protocol involved a secondary operationalization of indicators derived from available assessments, which may introduce a degree of approximation in the interpretation of nonverbal dimensions.

Another limitation is represented by the possible influence of uncontrolled contextual factors, such as family involvement, prior therapeutic experience of the children, or variability in cognitive functioning within the IQ range of 50–54. These factors may modulate the response to intervention and contribute to variability in outcomes.

Additionally, the correlational analysis (Spearman's ρ) highlights significant relationships between variables but does not allow for the establishment of direct causal relationships. Thus, although the results support the conceptual model **fine motor skills** → **visuomotor imitation** → **expressive language**, they should be interpreted with caution in the absence of further experimental analyses.

Finally, it should be noted that the intervention was implemented in a specific (educational and therapeutic) context, which may limit replicability in other settings (e.g., family or different institutional environments), where resources and implementation conditions may vary significantly.

Therefore, these limitations do not invalidate the findings but emphasize the need for future research involving larger samples, randomized experimental designs, longitudinal assessments, and diversified measurement instruments in order to strengthen the evidence regarding the effectiveness of the SPSC-TSA model.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study support the effectiveness of the structured psychoeducational intervention, operationalized through the SPSC-TSA model, in enhancing communication development in children aged 5–6 years with autism spectrum disorder. The significant progress observed in the experimental group, compared to the more limited development in the control group, indicates that systematic, structured interventions tailored to the child's developmental profile can generate substantial improvements in communicative functioning.

A particularly relevant finding is the identification of visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills as pivotal abilities in the emergence and development of expressive language. These dimensions do not operate in isolation but are integrated within a functional model of the form **motor skills** → **imitation** → **language**, in which the development of fine motor control facilitates imitation abilities, which in turn support the emergence and consolidation of verbal behaviors. This relationship confirms an integrative perspective on language development, in which sensorimotor and communicative components are deeply interdependent.

The significant differences identified between groups at posttest, as well as the positive and significant correlations among the analyzed variables, support the need for an integrative psychoeducational approach. Effective intervention cannot target language as an isolated system but must simultaneously address the motor, imitative, and cognitive components involved in communication. From an applied perspective, the findings provide strong arguments for the systematic inclusion of visuomotor imitation and fine motor exercises in intervention programs designed for children with ASD. The SPSC-TSA model thus emerges as a coherent operational framework that can guide both speech therapy and psychoeducational practice, facilitating the design of personalized and effective interventions.

Overall, the study contributes to strengthening an integrative paradigm in special education, highlighting that the development of expressive language in children with ASD is the result of dynamic interactions among motor, imitative, and cognitive processes, rather than the outcome of unidimensional interventions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the obtained results, it is recommended to implement structured interventions in educational and therapeutic settings, to use progressive exercises targeting visuomotor imitation and fine motor skills, to integrate visual supports, to promote interdisciplinary collaboration between psychoeducators and speech therapists, and to ensure continuous monitoring of children's progress.

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